

Studies on the Precipitation of Lanthanum and Cobalt Oxalates and its Gravimetric Applications

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Precipitation of lanthanum and cobalt as oxalates has been studied individually and in combination. Individually lanthanum and cobalt oxalates exist as deca- and dihydrates respectively, but the combined oxalate is only a hexahydrate. The compositions are also confirmed by thermogravimetric analysis. Quantitative precipitation of cobalt oxalate is effected by decreasing the dielectric constant of the precipitating medium with acetic acid. Cobalt oxalate can be precipitated at higher pH by using non-interfering bases such as lutidine for pH adjustments. Lanthanum oxalate can be selectively and quantitatively separated from cobalt by complexing the latter with ammonium oxalate. Procedures are suggested for the simultaneous gravimetric analysis of lanthanum and cobalt in presence of each other.

Lanthanum cobaltate, LaCoO_3 , is presently being pursued to replace the noble metal catalysts for oxidation of CO, hydrocarbons and reduction of nitrogen oxides¹ and also for other reactions². One of the common methods of preparing this compound is through decomposition of the combined oxalates after coprecipitation from a solution containing cobalt and lanthanum. Incomplete precipitation of cobalt is a significant factor which affects the stoichiometry of the final product³. Efforts are being made from time to time to bring improvements in the oxalate method⁴ but it is interesting to note that even a suitable gravimetric method involving the precipitation of oxalates for the determination of lanthanum and cobalt in lanthanum cobaltate is not yet available. This may be due to inconsistencies in the composition of lanthanum oxalate or incomplete precipitation of cobalt oxalate. The present method aims at developing conditions for the quantitative precipitation of the oxalates of lanthanum and cobalt and their quantitative determination individually and in the presence of each other.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) indicate quantitative separation of lanthanum as $\text{La}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and cobalt as $\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from solutions containing these metal ions. However, conditions were stringent in the case of lanthanum for recoveries conforming to the suggested formula. In the case of cobalt, the precipitating medium plays an important role⁵, e.g. acetate reduces the dielectric constant of the medium⁶ and also the solubility of cobalt oxalate. We obtained results similar to that of acetate (Table 1) by replacing it with propionic acid or dioxane, the reagents well-known for decreasing the dielectric constant of a medium⁷.

The precipitation of cobalt as its oxalate could be completely prevented by adding excess ammonium/potassium/sodium oxalate (Table 2) due to formation of water soluble anionic complexes⁸, such as $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3]^{2-}$ or

$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{4-}$. Davitashvili and Modebadze⁹ made similar observation on manganese oxalate. Approximately known quantities of lanthanum present in a La-Co mixture could be estimated by adding a 50% excess ammonium oxalate at pH 4.0 followed by immediate filtration. Delay in filtration results in contamination with cobalt oxalate. Interestingly, the combined precipitate of lanthanum cobalt oxalate formula conforms to $\text{La}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3 \cdot \text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Accordingly, the lanthanum oxalate values (Table 2) are computed from the experimentally obtained La_2O_3 values and expressed as $\text{La}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for convenience. Cobalt is found by difference. The results (Table 2, sl. nos. 7-10) reveal that very accurate values are obtained even when the combined oxalates are weighed as such. Sl. nos. 11,12 (Table 2) indicate the applicability of the method to lanthanum cobaltate samples.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COBALT OR LANTHANUM BY THE OXALATE METHOD*

Sl. no.	$\text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Obtd. (mg)	Co_3O_4 Obtd. (mg)	$\text{La}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Obtd. (mg)	La_2O_3 Obtd. (mg)
1.	95.0 (95.1)	41.6 (41.7)	185.1 (185.9)	83.3 (83.9)
2.	190.3 (190.2)	83.5 (83.5)	373.1 (371.8)	167.8 (167.8)
3.	380.4 (380.5)	167.0 (166.9)	746.4 (743.5)	335.7 (335.6)
4.	570.9 (570.9)	250.4 (250.4)	1113.0 (1115.3)	503.2 (503.4)

*Values in the parantheses are the expected values.

Conversion factors for oxalate to metal - Co : 3.1038, La : 2.5982.

Conversion factors for oxide to metal - Co : 1.3620, La : 1.1728.

Ammonium oxalate or oxalic acid may be used for washing lanthanum oxalate but the former forms soluble complexes with cobalt and hence not recommended for cobalt oxalate. When lanthanum is selectively precipitated in the presence of cobalt only ammonium oxalate may be used as wash solution as oxalic acid may bring down the pH resulting in the breakdown of the complexes and coprecipitation of cobalt oxalate. Samples of the combined precipitate can also be prepared at varying pH values by

TABLE 2—SIMULTANEOUS GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF LANTHANUM AND COBALT BY OXALATE METHOD*

Sl. no.	La taken (mg)		Co taken (mg)		La obtd. (mg)		Combined La + Co (mg)		Co by difference (mg) as	
	oxalate	oxide	oxalate	oxide	oxalate	oxide	oxalate	oxide	oxalate	oxide
	as	as	as	as	as	as	as	as	as	as
1	—	83.9	95.1	41.7	—	83.7	—	—	—	—
2	—	167.8	190.2	83.5	—	167.9	—	—	—	—
3	—	335.6	380.5	166.9	—	336.0	—	—	—	—
4	—	503.4	570.7	250.4	—	502.9	—	—	—	—
5	—	83.9	95.1	41.7	—	83.8	—	—	—	—
6	—	503.4	570.9	250.4	—	503.8	—	—	—	—
7	158.1	83.9	95.1	41.7	158.5	84.0	253.4	125.7	94.9	41.7
8	316.1	167.8	190.2	83.5	316.7	167.9	507.1	251.3	190.4	83.4
9	632.2	335.6	380.5	166.9	630.7	335.6	1010.8	502.4	380.1	166.8
10	984.4	503.4	570.7	250.4	954.7	503.1	1522.9	753.7	569.2	250.6
11	312.1	165.7	186.0	81.6	312.5	165.9	498.8	247.6	186.3	81.7
12	998.8	530.2	595.1	261.1	999.8	530.7	1594.0	791.8	594.2	261.1

*Each value is an average of four experiments.

Conversion factor for lanthanum oxalate to metal (sl. nos. 7–12) : 2.2094

employing triethylamine at pH < 5.0 and lutidine at even pH > 7.0 depending upon the dictates of catalyst requirements.

Preliminary studies : The studies indicate that precipitation of lanthanum oxalate upto 98% occurred even at pH < 1.0 and was instantaneously complete at pH > 2.5. Only 90% cobalt was precipitated out by employing oxalic acid. Ammonium oxalate at pH > 2.5 and a cobalt-to-ammonium oxalate ratio of 1 : 1.2 brought out complete precipitation of cobalt. Ammonium oxalate also improved the physical characteristics of lanthanum oxalate precipitate. Excess of these reagents had contrasting effects on cobalt. While in the case of ammonium oxalate precipitation decreased from 100% to nil for 1.2 to 8 times excess respectively oxalic acid had a positive effect with precipitation becoming rapid and increasing with increasing amounts. The precipitation of cobalt was inhibited by ammonia at excess reagent concentrations and triethylamine at higher pH (>5.0). Lutidine (2,6-dimethylpyridine), a non-interacting base¹⁰, did not interfere with precipitation even at pH >7.0. In the presence of 5–20% glacial acetic acid, propionic acid or dioxane, cobalt oxalate was found to be practically insoluble.

TG-DTA studies indicate the cobalt oxalate as a dihydrate and the lanthanum oxalate as a decahydrate when precipitated individually. Interestingly, the combined oxalate is only a hexahydrate with dehydration commencing at 130° to be completed before oxalate decomposition. If the precipitates are to be weighed as oxalate hydrates, the drying temperature may, therefore, not exceed 100°. The decomposition of cobalt oxalate begins at 270° with the release of CO and CO₂. In contrast, the decomposition of lanthanum oxalate begins at a higher temperature. The TG-DTA curve of the mixed oxalates shows a stepwise decomposition indicating the presence of both the oxalates as separate entities in the composition. These are consistent with the reported data¹¹.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. Lanthanum and cobalt solutions (0.1 or 0.2 M) were prepared from their nitrates. Solution of lanthanum cobaltate was prepared by dissolving lanthanum cobaltate (1 g) in 1 : 1 HCl (100 ml). The lanthanum and cobalt contents were estimated by the complexometric method¹². Oxalic acid or ammonium oxalate as solid or 0.1–0.5 M solutions were used as source for oxalate ions. pH of these solutions was adjusted to the required value using dilute solutions of ammonia, lutidine or trimethylamine.

Thermal analysis was carried out on a Shimadzu DT30 automatic thermal analyser in static air at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹.

Procedure :

Estimation of cobalt : A solution of cobalt (30–180 mg) and 10% oxalic acid (2.5 ml) was made upto 50 ml, heated on a boiling water-bath for ~3 h. The resulting precipitate was washed with oxalic acid solution (0.1 M) and distilled water and dried at 100° for 4 h in an air-oven before weighing as CoC₂O₄·2H₂O. Alternatively, the precipitate was first dried in an air-oven at 100° for ~2 h and then transferred to silica or platinum crucible. The precipitates were ignited at 800° or above for 4 h before weighing as Co₃O₄.

Estimation of lanthanum : A solution of lanthanum (70–420 mg) and oxalic acid (25 ml) was diluted to 50 ml. Following the above procedure, results for lanthanum as La₂(C₂O₄)·10H₂O or La₂O₃ were obtained.

Estimation of lanthanum in presence of cobalt : A solution (50 ml) of cobalt (30–180 mg), lanthanum (70–420 mg) and ammonium oxalate (5 g) was taken and the precipitation was carried out following the above procedure. The resulting precipitate was washed with 0.1 M ammonium oxalate, dried and ignited as above.

Combined estimation of lanthanum and cobalt : A solution (50 ml) of cobalt (30–180 mg), lanthanum (70–

420 mg), glacial acetic acid (2.5 ml) and oxalic acid (2.5 g) was taken. Following the above procedure, the precipitate obtained was dried and/or ignited. The known values for lanthanum oxalates were expressed as $\text{La}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for convenience in Table 2 which includes the results of combined estimation (Sl. nos. 5–8).

Conclusions : (i) Cobalt can be quantitatively precipitated as its oxalate by decreasing the dielectric constant of the precipitating medium. (ii) Lanthanum can be precipitated selectively and quantitatively as its oxalate in the presence of cobalt by forming the anionic cobalt complex. (iii) Combined precipitation of lanthanum and cobalt as their oxalates yields a composition $\text{La}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3 \cdot \text{CoC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suitable for gravimetric determination in the same weighing form.

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References

1. A. V. SALKER, D. K. CHAKRAVARTY and H. V. KEER, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **28**, 458; H. ARAL, T. YAMADA, K. EGUCHI and T. SEIYAMA, *Appl. Catal.*, 1986, **26**, 265.
2. T. SHIMIZU, *Appl. Catal.*, 1986, **28**, 81.
3. U. R. MARWAH, P. RAMAKRISHNAN and T. K. S. MURTHY, 'Proc. Symp. on Sci. of Catal. and its Appln in Ind', FPDIL, Sindri, 1979, p. 17.
4. C. C. CHANG and H. S. WENG, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 1992, **31**, 1615.
5. K. KAWAGAKI, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1956, **77**, 1461 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, **52**, 2658).
6. H. P. BENNETO, D. FEAKINS and D. J. TURNER, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 1211.
7. "The Chemistry of Nonaqueous Solvents", ed J LAGOWSKI, Academic, New York, 1970, Vol. 3, p. 362, Y. MARCUS, "Ion Solvation". Wiley, New York, 1985, p. 86.
8. J. E. BARNEY, W. J. ARGERSINGER and C. A. REYNOLDS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3788; J. W. ADAMSON, H. OGATA, J. GROSSMAN and R. NEWBURY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 319.
9. E. G. DAVITASHVILI and M. E. MODEBADZE, *Izv. Akad. Nauk Gruz. SSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1986, **12**, 167.
10. J. G. PRITCHARD and F. A. LONG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 2365.
11. V. V. SUMBARAO, R. V. G. RAO and A. B. BISWAS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2575; O. K. SRIVASTAVA and V. MURTHY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, **29**, 470; D. DOLLIMORE, D. L. GRIFFITHS and NICHOLSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 473; K. NAG and A. ROY, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1976, **17**, 247; W. HUA, W. ZENG, Z. CHEN, X. WANG and L. LU, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1992, **197**, 259.
12. N. N. DAS, J. R. RAO, K. M. PARIDA and S. B. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 736.